

Why the common practices matter in smart cities

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Introduction

“The illustration of smart cities looks fantastic, but doesn’t seem to be realistic. There is a big gap between what people do in the neighborhoods and what the smart city strategy is striving for.”

- An interviewee at Science Meets
the City, Rotterdam

The smart city planning became a buzzword. Cities explored the possibility of technology to improve urban infrastructure for sustainability. As technological advancements and urban challenges have risen, cities started integrating technology with a range of urban challenges, such as public safety, air quality monitoring, transportation, and energy systems (ISO, 2016, 2019, 2021). Since 2010s, there has been a great deal of technological expansion, such as IoT, IoB, Big data, and AI. Cities have deployed various high-tech solutions into a smart city strategy, in other words, what smart cities aim for is to improve urban quality.

Some cities implement innovative technologies to enhance urban living, others establish the urban system for an efficient transportation system, or might be committed to sustainable urban development by using the technology. Thus the implementation of the smart city concept across the world is related to different practices that people share;

however, many cities seemed to overlook the importance of what common practices are there. Common practices refer to economic, social, and cultural practices that people share in a certain community/ city/ nation (Won, 2020). Common practices in Rotterdam, for instance, are different from those in Seoul. In Rotterdam, hands-on practice matters, yet, in Seoul, feasibility more matters. If so, the smart city strategy of each city might be culturally differently designed.

The contribution of this article, as a part of the editorial project initiated by KEA, is to shed light on a crucial point in question that many smart city schemes are missing: common practices. In the sense that the common practices in smart cities are involved in the question of how people's standards of living can be improved through different kinds of cultural activities, this issue better to be analysed with a cultural economics perspective, to find a proper way of valuing them (Rowe, J., and Barnes, 2013; Klamer, 2016; Won, 2020).

Methodology and empirical analysis

This study examines two cases of Sejong in South Korea and Rotterdam of the Netherlands. We examine in which ways smart city strategies connect to common practices in culture. By doing so, we deviate from the usual approaches that focus on technology deployment and governance issues of the data collection. The primary aim is to make sense of practices that smart city planners and users build by means of a descriptive analysis. To this end this study brings the Governing Knowledge Commons (GKC) framework, and focuses on Action Arena.

Figure 1
The Governing Knowledge Commons (GKC) framework
Source: Madison, Frischmann, and Starandburg (2010)

Following Ostrom’s insights, the GKC framework has been modified to elaborate the principles and practices which are accessible a by a certain community. The GKC framework enables cities to comprehend the ways in which people use the resources that are provided by smart tech (Frischmann, Madison, and Sanfilippo, 2023). This study reviewed a range of documentations, such as policy papers, white papers, academic articles, and master plans to analyze Action Arena, including limited secondary data and big data from social media, newspaper articles, and websites for the period 2005-2018, by means of a coding system, Atlasti.

Sejong in South Korea

Since the early 2000s, many South Korean cities have relied on smart tech deployment in a range of sectors, such as administrative systems, public services, urban development, education, social infrastructure, and even cultural sectors.

Recently, the smart city strategy has evolved with not only the government initiatives but also innovative entrepreneurs and smart users. The smart city pilot project of Sejong in particular got a great deal of attention. It is noting that Sejong is a new city, designed for an efficient administrative system as well as a balanced use of land. Two points may have to be carefully considered; first,

based on dozens of experiments with smart city solutions, Sejong city delivers a citizen-centric policy scheme with a more hands-on approach for beneficiaries; second, it provides a more connected smart tech deployment for the neighborhood than the previous strategies. For the sake of a range of civic engagement a series of subset projects has been set up. This recent approach, in contrast to the previous project development approaches, is to call for urban quality improvement in connection with users/ residents. So, understanding Action Arena with the common practices provides the stakeholders more pragmatic information.

Figure 2
Geographical
location of
Sejong Smart
City Pilot
Source: LH
Sejong Smart
City Pilot, 2018

To make sense of important qualities, this study, based on a large survey² initiated by the Korea Land and Housing Corporation, elaborated and categorized what values matter into three: cultural, social, and economic values. In particular this study focuses on the common practices in culture.

The Figure 3 addresses that there is a lack of common

² The survey was conducted in 2018, distributed to a representative sample of people aged 17 years or older. The sample size was 1,214. The questionnaire was designed to reflect five pillars: what matters in South Korean cities, what values matter in urban life, what is important to smart cities, what values matter in the new cities, and happiness in urban life (Governmental consortium, 2018)

practices in culture, specifically in happiness. It is noting that the common practices in culture are not simply about cultural activities per se, but they are more about what people do, according to which a smart city can realize its purpose by means of social and cultural practices in combination with smart tech.

Common practices in Smart city	
Cultural value	Happiness, Beyond materials, Eco-friendly urban design
Social value	Work and life balance, Open platform for dwellers, Sharing resources
Economic value	Creative innovation, Sustainable markets with the circular economy concept

Figure 3
Common practices for values in Sejong smart city
Source: authors' own elaboration

In this context Actors are more about individuals who engage in the different practices, such as artists, entrepreneurs, dwellers, and other relevant stakeholders who get involved in creative innovation. It is worth noting that this pilot is beyond a digitalization of the social and economic infrastructures to create possibilities to realize culture embedded in life for the citizens' wellbeing.

Rotterdam in the Netherlands

Rotterdam is one of advanced cities when it gets to smart cities strategies. Since 2014, the municipality of Rotterdam has strived for the smart city initiatives, aiming at driving innovation and sustainable development in collaboration with relevant stakeholders, such as the

municipality, businesses, research institutions, and citizens. The focus of this policy has been most likely to develop data platforms and sustainable energy management systems (Municipality of Rotterdam, 2022). Related to this scheme, the city promoted numerous experiments and hands-on practices. What is most important here is that the common practices in culture play an important role to push the boundaries in the society. The floating farm in Rotterdam is one of well-known hands-on practices within the smart city strategy. In response to food production and sustainability, the floating farm was designed to use automated systems and create sustainable practices for production of fresh dairy products while minimizing environmental impact. The focus here is that this project runs an educational center and cultural programs for visitors to raise awareness about sustainable urban farming and to give a concrete insight on what a circular economy means in the real life.

Figure 4. Floating Farm
Source: <https://floatingfarm.nl>

Common practices in Smart city	
Cultural value	Creative experiment for urban sustainability
Social value	Innovative approach to neighbourhoods, Open platform, Civic participation
Economic value	Creative innovation, Efficient energy system, the circular economy

Figure 6. Common practices for values in Rotterdam smart city
Source: authors' own elaboration

At a glance the role of practices in culture sound instrumental to support smart city strategies. However, according to the policy papers, the municipality combined technology with a various kinds of cultural practices in the vein of sustainability that is one of central purposes of the Rotterdam resilience strategy. Not only does the Digital City Platform contribute to deployment of the smart technology, but the associated practices also add values to support the civil society.

Discussion and Conclusion

In the early stage of the smart city initiatives, the planning concentrated on the technology development and digitalization of the urban systems. There has been an increasing gap between the initiators and the users/beneficiaries (Municipality of Rotterdam, 2022; Municipality of Sejong et al., 2018; Karimikia et al., 2022). In this vein, this study argues why the common practices matter in the smart city strategy to connect policy and the relevant communities.

It is interesting to discover that different cities have

different common practices. The two cases strive for the same goal. Yet, each case involves a specific practice with different values. The Sejong case proposes a human-centered urban environment by leveraging technology, innovation, and culture. The pilot sought to go beyond traditional utility-based understanding to building a smart city. As Sejong is a completely new city, the policy might have to be more receptive to potential dwellers who will inevitably come from a great variety of places. The approach that this article proposes provides a more receptive perspective to resolve the dilemmas between Actors, such as the original dwellers and new comers in a more feasible manner. This pilot is ongoing, and new technologies and innovations will continue to shape the project for a more futuristic and realistic urban quality.

The Rotterdam case shows a different story. The governance that the municipality tried to construct was to put greater focus on civic engagement with diverse hands-on approaches. With a focus of sustainable energy development under the circular economy, the initiators have developed dozens of action plans in collaboration with multiple stakeholders, including entrepreneurs, urban designers, research institutes, local communities, and artists. For instance, urban designers and research institutes explore the possibility for collaboration coming up with the civic engagement with respect to promoting knowledge transmission for the local communities (Municipality of Rotterdam, 2022).

The purpose of the smart city policies, in the end, has been to improve the quality of life for citizens. In order not to make smart city planning hype, cities need realistic approaches to involve the citizens. In this sense, building the common practices in culture is an expedient approach through which to make sense of different practices that

matter to the smart city planning. For the sake of empirical analysis, this study used two cases. However, more research is needed to categorize common practices in the general context to make them comparable in different cities in a more systematic way.

References

- Butot, V., Bayerl, P. S., Jacobs, G., & de Haan, F. (2020). Citizen repertoires of smart urban safety: perspectives from rotterdam, the netherlands. *Technological Forecasting & Social Change*, 158. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2020.120164>
- Frischmann, B., Madison, M., and Strandburg, K. (Eds.). (2014). *Governing knowledge commons*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Frischmann, B. M., Madison, M. J., & Sanfilippo, M. R. (Eds.). (2023). *Governing smart cities as knowledge commons* (Ser. Cambridge studies on governing knowledge commons). Cambridge University Press.
- ISO. (2016). *ISO 37101, Sustainable development in communities — Management system for sustainable development — Requirements with guidance for use*
- ISO. (2019). *ISO 37122, Sustainable cities and communities — Indicators for smart cities*
- ISO. (2021). *ISO 37106:2021 Sustainable cities and communities — Guidance on establishing smart city operating models for sustainable communities*
- Joshi, A., Turkay, C., & Laramée, R. S. (2018). Visualization for smart city applications. *Computer Graphics and Applications*, 38(5), 36–37. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MCG.2018.053491729>
- Karimikia, H., Bradshaw, R., Singh, H., Ojo, A., Donnellan,

- B., & Guerin, M. (2022). An emergent taxonomy of boundary spanning in the smart city context - the case of smart dublin. *Technological Forecasting & Social Change*, 185. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2022.122100>
- Klamer, A. (2016). *Doing the Right Thing: A Value Based Economy*. London: Ubiquity Press.
- Municipality of Rotterdam. (2022). *Resilient Rotterdam Strategy 2022-2027*
- Municipality of Sejong et al., (2019). *Sejong Smart City Pilot Planning*
- Rowe, J., & Barnes, P. (2013). *Our common wealth: the hidden economy that makes everything else work* (Ser. A bk currents book).
- Won, Y.S. (2020). *Assessing urban qualities within the new economy: A Value based approach to cities*, Rotterdam: Erasmus University Rotterdam.